

ENHANCING ENGLISH LANGUAGE ACCESSIBILITY VIA AI TOOLS IN PAKISTANI CLASSROOMS

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Abstract

This study explores how AI accessibility is playing its crucial role in enhancing English language learning, particularly in Pakistani classrooms. With the advancement in technology, AI tools in education, such as ChatGPT, Google Translator, grammar correction tools, Duolingo, etc. provide support in the process of English language learning. Theoretical framework TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) highlights the connection between AI tools and the users. By adopting a qualitative method, this research draws on structured interviews from university students of English department and class observation to unveil how learners are interacting with AI tools and which are the barriers that can affect language learning, particularly for those students who belong to underdeveloped areas with limited resources. Thematic analysis in this research identifies the similar and diverse perspectives and experiences of the individuals. However, this study also highlights the significant accessibility gaps of language practice, students' lower confidence, technology, teacher quality, resources, socioeconomic status, geographic location, language environment gap, and insufficient institutional support. This paper contributes to uncovering the advantages of AI tools in language learning and accessibility gaps, which can debilitate this process of learning.

INTRODUCTION

The word AI, which is currently more reliable among students, stands for artificial intelligence. AI means making computers or machines smart enough to perform tasks that normally need human intelligence. Ahmet (2018), as cited in Ghafar, ZanyarNathir, et al. (2023), says artificial intelligence is a combination of two phrases, "artificial" and "intelligence." The word artificial means made or produced by humans, while "intelligence" refers to the ability to understand or to learn. In that case, the term artificial intelligence collectively means the development of computer systems in such ways that require human intelligence to perform tasks. AI has made significant advancements in various fields such as education,

business, agriculture, and social media. It can help in accessing various languages, solving problems, making decisions, and other numerous works. In the innovative world where new technologies are being introduced rapidly, AI is being explored as a tool to enhance English language learning, particularly in Pakistani classrooms and multilingual countries. The integration of Artificial Intelligence in English Language Teaching has become a significant issue in today's evolving educational environment, (Khan, Farooq, & Khan, 2025). There are different kinds of AI language learning tools and websites. Among these, the frequently used tools include ChatGPT, Duolingo, Google, Gemini, Google Translate, Elsa

Speak, etc. Lately, the trend of using AI tools such as ChatGPT to learn the English language has increased among students. AI propounds personalized, interactive, and adaptive learning (Sari.N 2023). Samad (2012), as cited in Harry (2023), AI plays a crucial role in providing personalized learning. Through machine learning algorithms, it can learn and analyze students' learning patterns. AI tools such as chatbots (computer programs that talk to humans through text or voice), AI assistants, grammar checkers, and language applications (Duolingo, Babbel) are increasingly being used to support English language learners globally. As English is a global language. Accessing English language proficiency is crucial for students to get opportunities worldwide. It has been an integral part of Pakistan's official, economic, educational, and, in some contexts, social life since its creation in 1947. AI learning tools help students learn language as they are effective and easy to use (De la Vall& González Araya, 2023). Despite their efficiency and convenience, the effective implementation of AI in Pakistani classrooms faces several accessibility challenges, including infrastructural limitations, teacher training needs, linguistic diversity, etc. (Mehboob, 2009).According to Heil, Wu, Lee, & Schmidt (2016), a remarkable number of people are turning to their mobile devices to learn a foreign language. AI tools help students access a foreign language easily, as they only require a smartphone and good internet. According to DelaVall& González Araya (2023), automated translation tools, language tutoring tools, and language generation systems are different learning tools that make a language easier to understand and access. Translation tools such as Google Translate help in translating one sentence of a different language into your native or other foreign language. Grammar checkers, such as Grammarly, are automated proofreading systems that can highlight or identify grammatical mistakes (ONeil&Russel, 2019). Other than that, AI-driven tools also include gamified exercises to engage the user and various other experiences tailored to the learner's proficiency level and learning styles (Jegade, 2024).Furthermore, language learning applications provide interactive lessons, quizzes, pronunciation guides, and speaking practice to strengthen vocabulary and communication skills.Using these AI-driven tools, language

accessibility becomes easier. Language accessibility is indispensable in education, as it ensures that all the students, regardless of their educational or linguistic background, get equal access to education. It contributes to creating an inclusive environment where everyone is valued and supported. It says that one can easily access a language when he/she is familiar with the language.

This research explores how AI is enhancing English language accessibility and what some accessibility gaps particularly in Pakistani classrooms. Accessibility gaps refer to obstacles or barriers that can prevent people from accessing something. In the context of the article, the research unveils which are the barriers in Pakistani classrooms that students are still facing challenges in accessing digital technology. This research topic can also be connected to Linguistics, particularly the areas of Applied linguistics and Second Language Acquisition (SLA).

Literature Review:

In the previous section, we introduced certain AI-driven tools such as ChatGPT, Duolingo, grammar checkers, and other language-learning apps. Furthermore, the significance of language accessibility and why it matters in education was discussed. In this section, the objective is to study and summarize relevant studies. In addition, certain approaches will be given on how students and teachers can use AI-driven tools in their classrooms. The ultimate focus is on how Pakistani students utilize these tools to enhance their English language accessibility since Pakistanis' first language is not English. In recent years, the inclusion of artificial intelligence (AI) in education has increased, particularly in the field of language learning. As English is a global language, the demand for effective and accessible English language has increased, especially in South Asian regions like Pakistan. Rasheed, Zeeshan, and Zaidi (2017) discuss that Pakistan is a country that faces challenges like linguistic diversity, multilingual classrooms, and educational disparities. Students speak regional languages when they are at home. This can hinder their ability to speak in English in the classroom. Khan, Fareed, Hussain, and Hussain (2024) say that students constantly face anxiety and lack confidence when speaking English because they fear mistakes. Addressing these gaps requires a

multifaceted approach, such as including digital technology like artificial intelligence (AI) in education to support such students. It could help in enhancing English language accessibility across Pakistani classrooms. The use of AI tools, from intelligent tutoring systems and language learning apps to chatbots, could play a significant role in addressing these gaps. These AI tools can enhance learner engagement, personalize learning, and provide real-time feedback. This review explores existing literature on the role of AI in English language accessibility, with a focus on its potential to enhance learning in Pakistani classrooms. Furthermore, the study highlights the limitations identified globally, setting the stage for understanding how artificial intelligence (AI) can meet the needs of Pakistani learners. Abu Sahyon et al. (2023) provide a comprehensive review of how AI-driven tools such as chatbots are transforming English language learning. Their study emphasizes that AI tools foster learner-specified environments by providing quick feedback. In addition, AI tools provide personalized learning and language practice opportunities. Their study emphasizes that such AI tools can help and support students in vocabulary building, grammar correction, and correct pronunciation. In this way, the students feel confident while sitting in a classroom. Ghafar et al. (2023), in his literature review, emphasized the influence of artificial intelligence (AI) on English language learning, exploring that AI tools are changing traditional educational learning. Their study highlights that AI has the ability to support skill development. Sari (2023) highlights that AI-driven tools can adapt to learners' needs and preferences. Their study emphasizes the effectiveness of AI tools. Their study highlights that these tools provide real-time correction, thus encouraging great confidence in learners. Furthermore, Sari (2023) concludes that AI not only supports language accessibility but also enhances communication skills, making it a more valuable resource in modern language learning settings. De LA Vall and González Araya (2023) mentioned some key benefits of AI-driven tools, saying that they enhance learners' ability to take charge of their own learning process and focus on their language practice. The tools, such as ChatGPT and other chatbots, provide real-time feedback, as mentioned earlier. Furthermore, Chen (2024)

elaborated on AI's capacity to analyze learner performance. It means that AI tools analyze a learner's performance by comparing the learner's previous results with current performance to monitor progress or improvement over time. Additionally, AI tools can identify grammar mistakes, vocabulary or pronunciation mistakes to identify a learner's improvement. Chen (2023) also emphasizes that AI tools can make learning more learner-centered and more accessible. Collectively, all these studies highlight the role of AI in enhancing English language accessibility by providing personalized, learner-centered learning and accessibility. In a multilingual context like Pakistan, English is often associated with socio-economic mobility (Rehman, 2002), but a hurdle is that many students belong to rural areas, where they may not have enough access and knowledge about digital technology, and they have limited access to tech clubs. Pragmatically, in English language learning, accessibility gaps refer to the fact that not all students have equal resources to learn the English language effectively.

In Pakistani classrooms, the major accessibility gaps can be:

1. Language practice gap
2. Students' lower confidence gap
3. Technology gap
4. Teacher quality gap
5. Resources gap
6. Socioeconomic gap
7. Geographic gap
8. Language environment gap

Language Practice Gap:

As English is a global language, it connects individuals from various linguistic backgrounds just like a bridge. Proficiency in English enables people to communicate with different concerns of the world (Lodhi & Akash, 2019). The language practice gap indicates that a learner knows a language's rules but struggles with its practical implementations. The learner finds it hard to speak English fluently.

Students' lower confidence gap:

Unlike foreigners, we are not born and brought up speaking English. This is one of the major barriers in

the pursuit of speaking English (Nadeem et al. 2024). In Pakistani classrooms, most of the students are not confident enough to communicate in English publicly. They feel hesitation to speak.

Technological gap:

Technological gap in the context of language learning refers to the disparity between availability and the use of it in education. The gap is because many students do not have equal access to computers or smartphones required for digital learning. In the region of Pakistan, lack of quality internet access makes it challenging for the learner to have proper access to digital learning apps like Duolingo.

Teacher quality gap:

Significant and well-trained teachers are the crucial part of language learning. Many English teachers, particularly in the underdeveloped areas of Pakistan (Baluchistan), lack specialized training in English language teaching. Most of the schools in rural areas do not provide ongoing trainings; therefore, the language instructors remain unaware of updated tools. Another gap can be that untrained teachers rely on outdated methods such as grammar translation methods rather than focusing on communicative techniques.

Resources gap:

This gap indicates how students face unequal access to learning material. In Pakistan, public institutions may face unequal distribution of funds. Schools in urban areas are well accommodated; on the other hand, schools in rural areas are not well organized. These resource gaps can include unequal access to textbooks, digital tools, libraries, organized labs, and engaging classroom environments. These limited budgetary policies often fail to maintain an effective language education (Zheng, Y. 2024). In the Pakistani context, students in a private school (Beaconhouse) have access to English libraries, computers, digital learning apps, and specialized language assistants. In contrast, a student of a public school that is located in a rural area may only have a whiteboard and an outdated textbook. These gaps can hinder the creativity level of students.

Socio-economic gap:

Low-income families often come up with the challenges either to meet basic needs or to provide quality education for their children (Zheng, 2024). Quality English language courses are often offered by private institutes, which make them difficult to afford for a family who is struggling with low income. A student in Islamabad uses AI learning apps, watches English movies, and attends a high-ranking private school with an engaging environment. This will make it easier for him to learn English effectively. In contrast, a student who belongs to a rural area may not have access to a computer, mobile, or well-trained language tutor; this may make it hard for him to grasp the English language easily.

Geographical gap:

Geographical gaps include differences in having opportunities between students living in different regions like rural or urban. Urban schools are updated, and rural schools face difficulties. Students living in developed or urban areas perceive English better as compared to the students who are living in underdeveloped areas. Learners who belong to cities have a higher skill in vocabulary than those living in coastal or rustic areas (Yusri&Hidayat, 2016). Urban areas are having access to more robust infrastructure, while rural areas confront various challenges that impact their quality English language learning (Zheng, 2024).

Language environment gap:

Language learning is a process of interaction with the environment. When we communicate with people, we learn more, but the hurdle is that we don't create an engaging environment and feel hesitation in speaking English.

Theoretical Framework, TAM (Technology Acceptance Model):

TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) is a model developed by "Fred Davis" that elaborates on how users come to accept technology and use a technology and why people choose to use or not use a new technology. In history, technology has greatly affected the way people accomplished their personal and professional objectives (EBSCO Information

Services, 2024). The key components of the TAM model are

Perceived Usefulness (PU): It refers to how much a person believes that using particular technology would enhance the things or help them do better in their work.

Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU): It explains how much users believe that the technology is easy to use or operate. Perceived ease of use has a causal effect on perceived usefulness (Davis, 1989).

Attitude toward use: It shows the attitude or feelings of the user toward using a technology (positivity or negligence).

Behavioral intention to use: It means the decision, plan, or choice of a person to use the technology.

Actual System Use: This refers to the practical use of technology.

By applying TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) a theoretical framework, we can easily understand how much AI is beneficial for English language learning and why learners and teachers may or may not accept AI tools like ChatGPT and Duolingo, particularly in Pakistani classrooms.

If we analyze according to the perceived usefulness, the students believe that by using AI chatbot, they can acquire the English language more efficiently. ChatGPT provides learners with required content.

On Grammarly, you individuals can check the grammar mistakes that they make while writing English. By using QuillBot, students can rephrase their content. Speaking practice also becomes very accessible via using AI speaking practice apps where you can talk freely, have conversations, and get feedback instantly.

In the lens of perceived ease of use, if the AI tools are easy to use, then they would be very beneficial for the learners in English language learning. If the applications have comprehensible interfaces and support regional languages as well, they are supposed to be accepted more.

In Pakistan, most of the students take advantage of AI tools, but still there are some students who face challenges such as a lack of quality internet and trouble in understanding digital systems.

AI can help students to enhance their English language skills, which would polish their motivation to learn the language and their proficiency in grammar, vocabulary, reading, and writing

(Annamalai, 2024; Annamalai et al., 2023), as cited in Xiaofan&Annamalai, 2025. If the technology is easy to use, then the learner will develop a positive attitude toward using it, but if the technology is difficult to use, such as if the language of a learning app is too complex to understand, then the learner, especially the beginner, may not be able to benefit from that app.

After experiencing an app, the learner would make a decision that either this AI tool should be used or not. This is behavioral intention toward any AI technology.

The use of technology or having benefited from it in the real world is the actual use of the system. For instance, using any English learning app for better practice. Tools that are used in technology enhance the ability of learners to write and read because they are user-friendly (Altun&Khurshid Ahmad, 2021). The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) helps us consider how technology is being accepted and how students are using it in the context of learning English, particularly Pakistani students. We can also analyze whether the technology is facilitating or debilitating us by developing complete reliance on AI tools.

Methodology:

Research design:

This section investigates how much individuals are operating AI tools, which type of tools are the most common and used frequently among Pakistani students, and why. This study adopts a qualitative method of research to identify the role of AI tools in English learning classrooms. Additionally, a pie chart and bar charts are added to further understand the use of AI among students. Thematic analysis is used to analyze the gathered data from interviews.

Participants:

The participants are the students of University of Okara from English Department who use AI tools for having access to the English language. Multiple questions related to AI tools are asked, and they elaborate their answers pragmatically according to their experiences and needs in using AI tools. Approximately, 40 students are involved in this interview.

Sampling Technique:

In this qualitative research method, purposive sampling technique has been used, in which selected students of specific knowledge and experience regarding the use of AI tools are asked the questions. They were the students of English department at University of Okara. The ultimate goal of this technique is to collect in-depth insights of learners who have multiple experiences of using AI tools and how these tools are beneficial for them in their language learning.

Data collection:

A structured interview was conducted. When the questions were asked, the answers were noted down at the time for in-depth analysis. The participants were instructed to take as much time as they can so that they can easily describe their perspectives on using AI tools and how much these tools are helpful in learning. Moreover, class observation was carried out to analyze how much students were indulged in and rely upon AI tools in some ways of learning English.

Data Analysis:

This research process is categorized into different parts, such as making multiple questions for the interview and educating respondents about the objectives of the interview. Thematic analysis is used to understand similar and different responses from the participants.

Ethical consideration:

This study prioritizes the protection of participants' identity, ensuring their concurrence to respond. Possible limitations are imposed, such as generalization due to limited participants from a particular area or institution.

Delimitations:

This research focuses on the English language students at higher education level in Pakistan and only includes those who are aware of AI tools and have some experience of using them. The study does not include the perspectives of language teachers and mainly focuses on individuals who use AI tools for English language learning.

Research Questions:

1. Have you ever used any AI tool for learning the English language? Which type of AI tools you have used and why?
2. How much have you found that AI tools are beneficial for learning the English language, particularly in Pakistani classrooms? Should we add AI tools in English language curriculum? Why or why not?
3. Do you feel that using AI tools is enhancing your English language capability and which skill do you want to develop by using AI tools?
4. Which type of difficulties or gaps are you facing while using AI tools?

Results and Discussion:

Similar Themes:

Commonly used AI tools
Perceived advantages of AI tools
Self-Motivation
Development of language skills
Positive suggestions of adding AI tools in the English curriculum

Contrary Ideas:

AI tools lessen the learners' own creativity level.
Over reliance on AI tools
Lack of practical conversation
Paid limitations of AI tools
Multiple difficulties while using AI tools

Commonly used AI tools:

The majority of the students shared their experience of using AI tools such as ChatGPT, Meta AI, DeepSeek, Gemini, Duolingo, Google Translator, Grammarly, QuillBot, etc. They have been using these AI tools for more than 2 to 3 years for English language learning. These tools are being frequently used among Pakistani students. They found these AI tools very effective for English language learning and easy to use. One of the respondents said: "AI tools are making language learning more accessible to a new learner."

Figure 1: Most commonly used AI tools for English Learning

Perceived advantages of AI tools:

Pakistani students shared their experience of using AI tools. They argue that AI tools make their English language learning easier and more comprehensible. They preferred ChatGPT for academic purposes, for asking grammar-related questions, and for finding

help in essay writing, letter writing, or application writing. Students just command AI tools to do what is required, and they get what they need. One of the students said:

“When I want to generate a formal text or message for a teacher, these AI tools help me a lot in formal settings.”

Figure 2: Areas of Language Improvement through AI tools among students

When it comes to writing, Pakistani students seek help from AI tools. Grammarly or QuillBot is frequently used to correct grammatical mistakes and for paraphrasing. Some applications, such as Duolingo, ELSA Speak, etc., help students speak English fluently and accurately. These apps provide one-to-one communication. Students get improvement in vocabulary, pronunciation, accent, sentence structure, etc.

Self-Motivation:

Students get motivated when they find the English language easier with the help of AI tools. They yearn to get command of this language. They put effort into building advanced vocabulary, fluency, etc. They use AI tools for academic research as well. Students can, on the spot, get suggestions and feedback from AI tools if there is any mistake or need for improvement. Another interviewer said:

“AI tools are quite beneficial in Pakistani classrooms as they turn complex things into much smoother things.”

Learners explore more AI tools for fun or for getting various ideas that uplift their interest in learning the English language.

Development of language skills:

Students use various AI tools for different reasons. This can be easily understood through a pie chart mentioned below:

Figure 3: Common purposes of using AI tools

Many students mention that they are enthusiastic to develop their skills through the use of AI tools. The majority of the students want to develop their writing and speaking skills. In writing, they can get their sentence structure and grammar corrected with the help of AI, and they can also write in a scholarly way. They argue that AI tools help them a lot when it comes to formal writing. In speaking, English language learners can maintain fluency via communicating with AI tools. They can communicate on any topic, anytime, or as much as they can. This practice of speaking helps them a lot, enhancing their speaking skill. One of the students said:

“As a bilingual student, I want to be a fluent English

speaker.”

Positive suggestions about AI:

Many Pakistani students strongly recommended that some AI tools should be a part of our English curriculum because, as non-native English learners, these tools are beneficial for learning. Students from underdeveloped areas or with a lack of resources are not aware enough of how to use these tools. As the world is evolving and adopting new technology, students must have knowledge about the latest AI tools for learning. There should be guidelines in the language classrooms about the usage of AI tools so that it would be helpful for those students who struggle with English.

Figure 4: Positive suggestions of students to include AI tools in English language Curriculum
Lessen the creativity level:

English language learners, particularly in Pakistani classrooms, are increasingly dependent on AI tools, which lessen their creativity. Instead of writing anything on their own, students simply copy from AI tools such as ChatGPT, which can harm their internal capability of writing something unique by themselves. So this may be a negative factor of using too many AI tools for learning. They just command AI tools to do what they are struggling with. One of the learners said: "AI tools are increasing the gap between what students can do on their own and what they can do with the help of these tools."

Few of the interviewers suggest that students should not totally rely on AI tools.

Lack of practical conversation:

Speaking practice via AI tools can both facilitate and debilitate the learner. If the learner is habitual to communicating with just AI tools, he may find it challenging to speak publicly. It might be difficult for him to have practical or everyday conversation with people. But if the learner communicates more with people and seeks AI tools for pronunciation or sentence correction, then it can be beneficial for him to speak confidently and fluently.

Difficulties or gaps while using AI tools:

As the AI tools are helping out the students in their language learning journey, there are still some obstacles or gaps that students are facing. One of the major difficulties is the free limitation of AI tools.

The paid version of these AI tools has outstanding features, but not everyone can purchase these tools. This can affect the language learning to some extent. AI tools also require internet connectivity to work, but in some areas where the internet connection is not available but there is a need to do a task, then this can be a hurdle in learning.

Some students are facing the hurdle that the data that AI presents is not authentic or reliable enough about some topics. Some applications are designed with complex language, which makes it difficult for a new learner to understand properly.

This thematic analysis clearly shows how AI is being operated among Pakistani students. There are multiple perspectives about the usage of AI tools.

Conclusion:

In the era of technological advancement, AI tools are proving helpful in the process of English language learning. The findings reveal how AI tools such as ChatGPT, Duolingo, QuillBot, and text-to-speech AI tools contribute to improving writing, speaking, reading, or listening skills, as well as enhancing grammar, pronunciation, accent, and vocabulary. Although these tools are making language learning easy and smooth, students should not be completely dependent on these tools. They should use these tools to some extent because overreliance on these tools can decline creativity levels. However, by using AI tools wisely, we can access better language learning in Pakistani classrooms.

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